

D2.2 Scientific advancements in understanding mechanisms underlying seasonal-to-decadal climate predictability

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents research conducted within the framework of ASPECT WP2 to address increasing the level of confidence in climate predictions through improved understanding of mechanisms (Task 2.2) and by accounting for model deficiencies (Task 2.3).

Skill scores reflect an integrated summary of the forecast assessment, but the origin of skill is sometimes difficult to interpret. Further, current forecast systems underestimate the predictable climate variations compared to the total variability (e.g. Smith et al., 2020). To understand the mechanisms underlying predictability and why the signal-to-noise ratio is too small in current forecast systems is key for correcting forecast error and would reduce uncertainties in regional climate information. In Task 2.2, a couple of process-based mechanisms are presented improving the understanding of prediction skill.

Further, the usability of near-term climate forecasts is limited by the misrepresentation of key physical processes and other model deficiencies, including very different responses to the same forcings, that significantly limit the actual predictive skill, understanding the mechanisms, and the usability of the forecasts. Moreover, it has been shown that state-of-the-art models cannot realistically simulate the predictable components of climate variability and consequently they exhibit substantially lower signal-to-noise ratios compared to observations. This salient problem has been diagnosed in various aspects of the predictions transecting different time scales. This task aims to evaluate the role of signal-to-noise deficits and that of other model deficiencies in relation to European climate predictability.

The key processes considered here are Rossby Wave Sources and their influence on precipitation over Northern Europe (SMHI), the ocean–atmosphere interaction and its role for the decadal predictability of the NAO (CMCC), the role of the North Atlantic sub-decadal variations for European summer climate (MPG) and how external forcing relates to the NAO and North Atlantic climate (Met Office, MPG). With regards to the NAO, it was found that some of the model spread was caused by differences in background water vapour, allowing an emergent constraint to be developed to better estimate the true response (Met Office). Further, an attribution approach has been developed to link extreme events to possible drivers with an emphasis on the Pakistan flood 2022 (UOX). ECMWF has evaluated trends in the tropical Pacific as represented by hindcasts for 1993–2019 of the coupled fifth generation seasonal forecasting system.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a bandwidth diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (along with uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (i.e., statistical methods, AI), HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing methods enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

There is a clear need to better understand the mechanisms and drivers of seasonal to decadal predictability. This would provide increased confidence in the forecasts and projections, diagnose model error, and understand signal to noise issues. It would also be a step towards developing integrated attribution and prediction, which is a central aim of the WCRP Lighthouse on Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change (Findell et al 2022). Here we summarise the key advances to this understanding made through ASPECT, covering aspects of seasonal-to-decadal climate to the role of external forcing.

2 Description of work

Global atmospheric response to Rossby wave sources over the Northeastern Pacific Ocean from a set of CMIP6 large ensembles (SMHI)

Rossby Wave Sources (RWS) originating over the northeastern Pacific shape the summer atmospheric circulation across the Northern Hemisphere, and how this teleconnection influences precipitation over Northern Europe (Fuentes-Franco et al, 2022). Using ERA5 reanalysis and a large ensemble of the EC-Earth global climate model, the study demonstrates that intensified Pacific RWS trigger a circumglobal wave-train pattern that modulates geopotential height, temperature, and rainfall along the Pacific–North America–Atlantic–European sector. A robust link emerges between strong Pacific RWS and enhanced summer precipitation over Northern Europe, particularly under cold Pacific and Atlantic SST states, when wave propagation toward Europe is more efficient. While in their study, Fuentes-Franco et al. (2022) demonstrated that the EC-Earth3 model broadly reproduces this large-scale response; the amplitude and spatial extent of the teleconnection depend on the background SST state and the model representation of mid-latitude circulation. These extended to other large ensembles produced by several global models provide a process-based foundation for evaluating how well global models simulate Pacific-driven teleconnections, an element directly relevant to ASPECT’s objective of improving large-scale drivers of European climate variability and predictability.

In ERA5, the RWS climatology displays coherent dipole structures that align with the upper-level subtropical jets and monsoon outflow regions. Prominent wave source regions appear over the eastern and central North Pacific, the Northeastern Atlantic, and the South Pacific, while sinks dominate the western ocean basins (Figure 1). These alternating bands of positive and negative RWS reflect the large-scale organization of tropical–extratropical interactions and the divergence–convergence patterns that sustain the stationary wave activity during summer. Most CMIP6 large-ensemble models reproduce these large-scale spatial patterns, although notable differences in intensity and position are evident. EC-Earth3 and CESM2 simulate RWS distributions that are closest to ERA5, with a realistic representation of the Pacific and Atlantic wave source-sink dipoles.

In contrast, CanESM5, IPSL-CM6A-LR and MIROC6 show enhanced magnitudes in the North Pacific sector, while NorCPM underestimates the strength of the RWS, particularly over the Northeastern Pacific. Some models exhibit zonal displacements or excessive latitudinal spreading of the subtropical RWS bands, which can be linked to biases in the position and strength of the upper-tropospheric jets and monsoon divergence.

Despite these inter-model discrepancies, all ensembles reproduce the main climatological characteristics of the RWS field during summer (JJA), indicating that the large-scale mechanisms of Rossby wave generation are robustly captured across models. However, the regional biases in amplitude and phase suggest that systematic errors in upper-level divergence, convective outflow, and jet dynamics may still contribute to model-to-model variability in teleconnection strength and spatial organization.

Figure 1. Climatological distribution of the Rossby Wave Source (RWS, -10^{-11}s^{-1}) during boreal summer (June–August, JJA) as derived from ERA5 and from a selection of CMIP6 large ensemble models. The number of ensemble members for each model is mentioned in parenthesis.

ERA5 reveals a well-defined circumglobal teleconnection response to enhanced Rossby Wave Sources (RWS) in the northeastern Pacific during boreal summer (Figure 2). When the Pacific RWS is higher than the climatological values, the Z500 field exhibits an alternating sequence of positive and negative correlation centers that trace a wavetrain along the mid-latitude waveguide of the Northern Hemisphere. This pattern begins with a positive Z500 anomaly over the northeastern Pacific, followed by a negative center over western North America, a positive center over eastern North America and Greenland, and a negative center over the North Atlantic extending into Northern Europe. Downstream, the wavetrain continues across Eurasia with alternating highs and lows before closing its arc over East Asia and the western Pacific. Physically, this structure reflects a stationary

Rosby wavetrain in which positive correlations correspond to an anomalous anticyclonic response (high pressure, subsidence, warm/dry anomalies), while negative correlations mark cyclonic anomalies (low pressure, ascent, and increased cloudiness or rainfall). Importantly for Europe, ERA5 shows a robust negative Z500 node over the North Atlantic–Nordic region, signifying that stronger Pacific RWS favor a cyclonic European summer pattern, consistent with enhanced storminess and wetter conditions over Northern Europe. This validates the mechanism proposed in the literature: Pacific upper-tropospheric forcing can project onto the Euro-Atlantic sector via a wavetrain that peaks in influence during summer.

Figure 2. Pearson correlation between the North Pacific Rossby Wave Source index (RWS over the North Pacific, see Fuentes-Franco et al. 2022) and 500-hPa geopotential height (Z500) during boreal summer (JJA) for ERA5 and the CMIP6 large-ensemble models. Red contours show significant values ($p < 0.05$). Units: dimensionless.

When compared with the reanalysis, the models all capture the existence of the wavetrain, but they differ in how accurately they reproduce its shape, amplitude, and phase. Some models tend to shift the downstream centers of action, especially over the North Atlantic–European region, where many simulations displace the negative node found in ERA5 either too far east toward eastern Europe (UKESM1-0-LL) or too far west over the central North Atlantic (IPSL-CM6A-LR). Other models underestimate the amplitude of the wavetrain, producing smoother and weaker Z500 anomalies that decay before reaching Europe, thereby diminishing the strength of the teleconnection over the Atlantic sector (NorCPM1). In contrast, a few models exaggerate the wave response over the Pacific and North America, leading to an over-energized upstream pattern that alters the downstream

phase over Europe (MIROC6 and IPSL-CM6A-LR). Among all ensembles, EC-Earth3 and CanESM5 provide the closest match to ERA5, maintaining the correct sequence and relative positioning of the Z500 anomalies, including a well-defined negative center over Northern Europe, which is essential for a realistic teleconnection.

A unifying feature across the ensembles is that the greatest spread and the largest deviations from ERA5 occur precisely over the North Atlantic–European node (including the lack of high positive correlation over Greenland). This indicates that the uncertainty among models is not primarily associated with the generation of the wavetrain in the Pacific, but rather with the maintenance and phasing of the wave as it crosses the Atlantic. Because this node controls the European circulation response, such phase errors directly modulate the models' ability to represent summer pressure and precipitation anomalies over Europe. This makes the Atlantic sector the key “bottleneck” of the Pacific–Europe teleconnection and underscores why its accurate representation is critical for improving European summer predictability.

Tropical Pacific Trends in the ECMWF Seasonal System (ECMWF)

Trends of observed tropical Pacific sea surface temperatures (SSTs) in recent decades have been toward a more La Niña–like state, i.e., SSTs warmed in the west Pacific and cooled in the eastern Pacific cold tongue and the southeastern subtropical Pacific, and easterly winds in the equatorial Pacific strengthened. These features are robust across different observational datasets and different periods across which the trends are computed. While a large body of literature addresses tropical Pacific SST trends in free-running coupled climate models, only a limited number of studies investigate this problem in the context of initialized seasonal hindcasts (i.e., retrospective forecasts). The analysis of trends in initialized forecasts complements the observational and free-running model studies, since it contains components of observations (in the initialization) and model behaviour (during the forecast). The time scale for development of trend errors in the forecasts provides valuable information on the short of process responsible for these trends or trend errors.

Here we evaluate trends in the tropical Pacific over 1993–2019 as diagnosed from SEAS5 hindcasts and assess how those errors affected predictions of the recent triple-dip La Niña during 2020–22. The present study goes beyond previous efforts by (i) pursuing a multivariate approach that allows for a more complete picture of underlying processes and (ii) diagnosing trends in a range of forecast experiments that allow us to disentangle the role of the atmospheric model, ocean initial conditions, and coupled feedbacks. This evaluation has been published as a peer reviewed paper ([Mayer et al 2025](#))

Figure 3 presents SST and 0–300-m ocean heat content (OHC) trends for November 1993–2019. Observed SSTs (Fig. 3a) have increased in large areas of the tropics, including the western and northern subtropical Pacific. An exception is the eastern equatorial and the southeastern subtropical Pacific, where observed trends are neutral or even weakly negative. We note that the overall trend patterns are present throughout the year (not shown). Observed OHC trends (Fig. 3d) share many features with SST trends, including the warming of the western Pacific and north of the equator.

Figure 3. Observed trends for November 1993–2019 of (a) SST and (d) 0–300-m OHC; SEAS5 ensemble mean trends for November 1993–2019 of (b) SST and (e) 0–300-m OHC; (c),(f) the trend error of the SEAS5 hindcasts. Stippling in (a) and (d) indicates statistically significant trends on the 90% confidence level; gray hatching in (a) and (d) indicates where trends are robust to outliers and contribute >10% to total variance; black hatching in (c) and (f) indicates where observations lie outside the 0.5th and 99.5th percentiles of all hindcast trends obtained from random sampling of ensemble members. Adapted from Mayer et al 2025.

In disagreement with observations, SEAS5 hindcasts show positive SST and OHC trends in the equatorial Pacific (Figs. 3b,e). Figures 3c and f show that observed SST and OHC trends in the equatorial Pacific are outside the central 99% of the hindcast-based trend distribution estimated from 1000 permutations of the ensemble members. However, OHC trend errors are less marked in the southeastern Pacific, suggesting surface processes (e.g., radiation, winds, evaporation) playing a role there.

Figure 4 presents (left column) observed, (middle column) hindcast, and (right column) forecast error trends for JJA 1993–2019. Observed zonal wind trends are toward stronger easterlies along the equator and in the southeastern Pacific, while in the northern subtropical Pacific, there is a westerly trend. Observed meridional wind trends display stronger southerlies peaking at the equatorial Pacific and extending into the northeastern and southeastern Pacific. The trends in cross-equatorial winds are consistent with decreasing (increasing) mean sea level pressure north (south) of the equator (not shown). The observed zonal and meridional wind trends together are consistent with the positive wind–evaporation–SST (WES) feedback, indicating a strengthening of the meridional SST gradient by the meridionally asymmetric zonal wind trends. The wind–evaporation–SST (WES) feedback describes a coupled mechanism by which an anomalous meridional sea surface temperature (SST) gradient in the tropics evolves over time. It can be positive or negative, depending on the dominant term in the air sea-interaction. The positive feedback is related with strong atmospheric response to SST gradients, while the negative feedback is related with enhanced momentum mixing across the boundary layer. See Karnuskas 2022 for more details

Trends toward stronger precipitation are observed in the western Pacific (consistent with zonal wind trends) and along the Pacific intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ; consistent with stronger southerly trends on the equator compared to north of it). Observed trends in Lower Tropospheric Stability lower-tropospheric stability (LTS = T700-SST, Fig. 4j) are positive over the southeastern Pacific, suggesting a more stable boundary layer, consistent with the cooling of the SSTs. This region also exhibits a negative trend in Absorbed Solar Radiation (ASR) which indicates an increase in cloud coverage that is consistent with the stabilization (Fig. 4m).

Figure 4. (left) Observed trends for JJA 1993–2019 of u10m (ERA5), v10m (ERA5), precipitation (GPCP), LTS (ERA5), and ASR (UoR); (center) as in (left), but based on SEAS5 (May start dates); (right) the trend error of the SEAS5 hindcasts. Stippling in (left) indicates statistically significant trends on the 90% confidence level; black hatching in (right) indicates where observations lie outside the 0.5th and 99.5th percentiles of all hindcast trends obtained from random sampling of ensemble members. From Mayer et al 2025.

SEAS5 hindcasts exhibit hardly any easterly trend along the equator and underestimate the westerly trends north of the equator (Figs. 4b,c) and strongly underestimate trends toward stronger southerly winds off the equator (Figs. 4e,f). The lack of meridionally asymmetric zonal wind trends (especially in 180°–120°W) in association with the underestimation of the positive trends in the meridional SST gradient suggests that the positive WES feedback is too weak in SEAS5. Consistent with SST (Fig. 3c) and wind trend errors, SEAS5 has a positive precipitation trend in the eastern Pacific and central Pacific, reaching the eastern edge of the warm pool (stronger than observed) rather than over the western part of the Pacific warm pool (cf. Figs. 4g,h), with the ensemble of trends being inconsistent with observations at many grid points in those regions (Fig. 4i). SEAS5’s LTS trends are negative along the equatorial Pacific, consistent with the spurious SST warming trend (i.e., destabilization and more precipitation along the equator). SEAS5 also underestimates the positive LTS trend and the associated negative ASR (i.e., more clouds) trend in the southeastern (SE) Pacific. Negative SEAS5 ASR trends in the eastern off-equatorial Pacific are generally weaker than those in observations, particularly around 10°N (Fig. 4o), where SEAS5 exhibits a negative

precipitation trend error (see Fig. 4i). Closer to the equator, where SEAS5 exhibits spurious tropospheric destabilization and precipitation increases (see Figs. 4l,i, respectively), ASR trend errors are small, indicating a rough balance of the shortwave radiative effects arising from trends in shallow and convective clouds in this region. The magnitude of the trend errors in surface heat fluxes is consistent with the error in the SST trends in Figure 3.

Mayer et al 2025 also investigate the relationship between the 1993–2019 trend errors and the forecast errors during the recent period 2020–22, during which a triple-dip La Niña event occurred, when most forecasts of that period pointed wrongly to termination of cool conditions in Niño-3.4. They show that ensemble mean forecast errors of winds and SST during these years are remarkably similar to the 1993–2019 trend errors.

The results presented so far raise several important questions. The neutral SST trends in observations in the presence of stronger easterlies are consistent with the paradigm of the ocean dynamical thermostat (Clement et al. 1996). This mechanism suggests that the otherwise uniform warming arising from greenhouse gas (GHG) forcing may partly be offset by the cooling arising from mean equatorial upwelling associated with the prevailing easterlies, which in return strengthens the zonal SST gradient and, in this way, further enhances easterlies and upwelling. An inspection of ORAS5 confirms that the upwelling in Niño3.4 has indeed increased. However, there are several questions to address associated with the ocean dynamical thermostat:

Has the cooling efficiency of the upwelling changed? The above reasoning assumes constant subsurface ocean temperatures, but inspection of subsurface temperature in Niño-3.4 based on ORAS5 data (not shown) indicates that the thermocline has warmed over 1993–2019, which suggests that the temperature of waters upwelled in Niño-3.4 has increased. This would mean a weakening of the ocean dynamical thermostat, i.e., that the cooling efficiency of the upwelling is decreased. An alternative interpretation is that subsurface warming trends in ORAS5 are spuriously generated by changes in the observing system, i.e., by a cold bias in the pre-Argo period that is alleviated later.

Which mechanisms lead to the changes in the atmospheric circulation responsible for strengthening of the easterlies and southerly surface winds? Reanalysis data indicate an increase in the stratification of the lower troposphere in the eastern equatorial and southeastern Pacific, which is associated with more low-level clouds and a reduction of the ASR. It is possible that this adjustment can enhance the zonal/meridional SST and surface pressure gradients and set up a new equilibrium for the Walker circulation. In SEAS5, the lack of easterly wind trends implies a lack of trends toward stronger upwelling (i.e., less cooling from this process). Another potential contributor to the positive SST trend in Niño-3.4 in SEAS5 hindcasts is the positive ASR trend error seen in the hindcasts relative to observations (see Fig. 4o).

In order to shed some light on these questions we conducted several sensitivity experiments to explore the origin of the trend errors in SEAS5. Below is a brief summary of the outcomes. For detailed information we refer to Mayer et al 2025.

We explored the role of the atmospheric model and its coupled feedbacks by assessing a set of uncoupled hindcasts with the same model version of SEAS5, but where the

ocean model is replaced by daily observed SST (SEAS5_obsSST). Wind trend errors of SEAS5_obsSST show similar features as those of SEAS5, which points to the atmospheric nature of the coupled model errors. To demonstrate how rapidly atmospheric trend errors develop we compare u10m and v10m trend errors in ERA5 12-hourly forecasts relative to ERA5 analysis. These can be considered very short lead time observed SST uncoupled forecasts. This comparison reveals that several of the essential wind trend features in the tropical Pacific are considerably weakened already at those short lead times. We also conducted experiments to assess the impact of changes in the ocean observing system ([Balmaseda et al 2024](#)). While the errors in the trends persist, results indicate that the ocean initial conditions can account for up-to 50% of the error in SST forecast trends in Nino-3.4.

Finally, we evaluated possible origins of the atmospheric forecast errors via regional relaxation experiments. Nudging the Southern Hemisphere extratropical atmosphere has a widespread impact also on tropical SST trends, inducing large-scale cooling of the equator and subtropical Pacific and Atlantic. This is associated with a substantial reduction of wind trends errors in the southern subtropical Pacific. However, the trend errors at the equator remain. This result suggests a role for the atmospheric bridge from the Southern Ocean to the tropical Pacific, consistent with [Kang et al. \(2023\)](#) who emphasized the atmospheric link between Southern Ocean SSTs with contemporary cooling trends in the southeastern Pacific via winds and clouds. Similarly, [Yeager et al. \(2023\)](#) showed that increased ocean resolution and resulting error reductions in the Southern Ocean lead to reduced SST trend errors in the tropical Pacific already in the first forecast year of initialized decadal predictions. However, the fact that in the IFS wind trend errors grow rapidly in the tropics but not in the southern extratropics contradicts the hypothesis that this mechanism is the primary cause of the found trend errors of SEAS5 in the tropics.

In summary, spurious atmospheric circulation trends of the uncoupled model have been identified as the root cause of the spurious decadal trends in SEAS5. Their apparent relationship with rapidly developing mean-state (wind and precipitation) biases suggests that trend errors may only improve upon further reduction of atmospheric model biases. Trends in anthropogenic aerosols cannot be discarded, but they have not been investigated here. The diagnosed trend errors in atmospheric circulation are amplified in the coupled SEAS5 hindcasts and aggravated by a potentially spurious subsurface warming of the equatorial Pacific in the initial conditions from ORAS5. This highlights the need for careful initialization of ocean reanalyses, especially in data-sparse times to avoid detrimental effects of the changing observing system on the homogeneity of the reanalysis record and subsequent initialized predictions. This work has immediate implications for further improvements of seasonal forecasting system, but given the similarity of trend errors of seasonal forecasts and free-running climate models not only in the tropical Pacific (e.g. [Beverley et al. 2024](#)), we propose that initialized seasonal forecasts may also represent a useful approach for testing and configuring climate models.

Sub-decadal coupled North Atlantic climate, European summer extremes and their predictability (MPG)

Extremely warm summers have a profound impact on human health, ecosystems, and the environment. Climate change is expected to further intensify these events, both in magnitude and frequency. Reliable climate predictions are therefore essential to improve preparedness for the risks associated with such extreme conditions. Advancing these predictions requires a deeper understanding of mechanisms and interactions within the Earth system, which in turn improves climate models and their projections.

Recent studies by MPG identify a physical mechanism that links variations in the coupled North Atlantic climate system to the occurrence of extremely warm European summers and their predictions (Wallberg et al., 2024; 2025). The mechanism is based on a forced delayed oscillation of the coupled system on a sub-decadal timescale. Here, NAO-like heat and momentum fluxes are suggested to redistribute North Atlantic water masses on a subdecadal to decadal time scale (Eden and Greatbatch, 2003; Reintges et al., 2017). As part of this oscillation, significant subdecadal variations in European summer temperatures and extremes are found in reanalyses, observations and model simulations (Müller et al., 2020, Wallberg et al., 2024). The link to European heat extremes begins several years before the heat events, with a strengthening of the North Atlantic subtropical gyre and increase of meridional ocean heat transport (as part of the redistribution of North Atlantic water masses due to the atmospheric forcing). This enhanced circulation leads to a gradual accumulation of ocean heat content in the upper 700m of the North Atlantic, particularly along the northern branch of the subtropical gyre (Figure 5). Over a period of two to three years, these positive ocean heat anomalies intensify and propagate northward, accompanied by a transition in the barotropic streamfunction, indicating a strengthening and poleward shift of the North Atlantic Current. As the ocean heat content reaches its maximum, typically in the year of the extreme summer, the heat is released to the atmosphere through enhanced upward surface heat fluxes. This ocean-to-atmosphere heat exchange warms the lower troposphere and reduces the meridional temperature gradient between mid- and high latitudes. As a result, the jet stream weakens and shifts northward, favouring the establishment of persistent high-pressure blocking systems over northern Europe (Figure 6). These circulation changes allow subtropical air masses to intrude farther north, substantially increasing the probability of extremely warm summers across Europe.

Figure 5: Extremely warm European summers and their relation to ocean quantities. (a) Upper 700 m ocean heat content. Anomaly of 5–10-year bandpass-filtered ocean heat content variability in MPI-GE for different lags prior to extremely warm European summers; values given in GJm^{-2} . (b) Ocean heat transport. Anomaly of 5–10-year bandpass-filtered ocean heat transport variability in MPI-GE for different lags prior to extremely warm European summers; values given in TW. (c) Barotropic stream function. Anomaly of 5–10-year bandpass-filtered barotropic stream function variability in MPI-GE for different lags prior to extremely warm European summers; values given in Sv. Contour lines indicate the mean state of the barotropic stream function; values given in Sv. All lags are given in years. Dots (a, c) and shading (b) denote significance at a 95 % confidence level. Period 1950–2022. (Adapted from Wallberg et al., 2024)

Figure 6: Extremely warm European summers and their atmospheric pathway. (a) Anomaly of 5–10-year bandpass-filtered Atlantic zonal mean temperature variability in MPI-GE during extremely warm European summers (lag 0); values given in K. (b) Anomaly of 5–10-year bandpass-filtered mean sea level pressure variability in MPI-GE during extremely warm European summers (lag 0); values given in hPa. The orange contour lines indicate the mean position of the jet stream (given by the mean zonal wind speed over 200–300 hPa) averaged over years showing an extremely warm European summer (solid line) and years showing no extremely warm summer (dashed line); values given in m s^{-1} . Dots denote significance at a 95 % confidence level. Period 1950–2022. (Adapted from Wallberg et al., 2024)

In a subsequent study, this mechanistic understanding was applied within a decadal prediction framework using large ensemble simulations of the MPI-ESM-LR model (Wallberg et al., 2025). The authors introduced a mechanism-based ensemble selection method, identifying and retaining only those ensemble members that display the characteristic sequence of North Atlantic precursor anomalies - from initial negative to subsequent positive streamfunction phases associated with ocean heat accumulation. This targeted selection significantly improved the predictive skill for Central European summer temperatures at lead times of up to a decade. Together, these studies provide a dynamical explanation of how sub-decadal ocean processes in the North Atlantic precondition the atmosphere for European heat extremes, and demonstrate how recognizing this mechanism can enhance the early predictability of such events.

Although the core studies focus on summer mean temperature extremes, this mechanism appears to be also directly relevant to other heat-related metrics such as growing degree-days (GDD). Here, GDD are calculated by the difference between daily maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) temperatures above a given baseline (T_{base}), where $T_{\text{base}}=10^{\circ}\text{C}$ and GDD set to 0 for values smaller than 0°C to 30 for values exceeding 30°C . Current work extends this analysis by explicitly linking the North Atlantic heat accumulation mechanism to variations in GDD, demonstrating its potential for early warning applications (Wallberg et al. in prep.). This ongoing research highlights that the ocean-heat-accumulation signal can serve as a precursor not only for mean-summer warming but also for impact-relevant extremes, such as high-GDD summers and maximum temperature anomalies, providing valuable lead time for agricultural and climate adaptation planning.

Decadal predictions outperform climate projections in forecasting Mediterranean wintertime precipitation thanks to better predicting the NAO variations (CMCC)

This part of the CMCC contribution is based on Nicoli et al. (2025). Decadal predictions (Init), initialized from November conditions, demonstrate superior skill compared to uninitialized simulations (NoInit) in forecasting Mediterranean wintertime precipitation for forecast years 1–10, with the improvements being more pronounced over Southern Europe (Iberian Peninsula, Balkans), Turkey, and North-East Africa (Figure 7, left). This enhanced predictability stems from the accurate initialization of the subpolar North Atlantic SST (SPNA-SST), where Init exhibits significantly higher anomaly correlation coefficients than NoInit, attributed to realistic initialization of the upper-ocean heat content. This leads to higher predictive skill also for the wintertime North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), which Init reproduces more skillfully ($\text{ACC}=0.58$ for years 1–10) compared to NoInit ($\text{ACC}=0.18$).

The NAO exerts a dominant control on Mediterranean wintertime precipitation variability through its influence on storm track position and intensity, with the negative NAO phase associated with enhanced precipitation over Southern Europe. The hybrid dynamical-statistical model, constructed using bilinear regression with predicted NAO and SPNA-SST indices as predictors, further enhances precipitation skill across Europe (Figure 7, right) by indirectly correcting for the weak ensemble-mean atmospheric signal, characteristic of the signal-to-noise deficit in climate predictions (Scaife and Smith 2018, Athanasiadis et al. 2020). This demonstrates that the superior performance of Init for Mediterranean precipitation is fundamentally linked to enhanced predictability of both SPNA-SST and the NAO index through initialization, with the NAO serving as the primary atmospheric teleconnection pathway transmitting North Atlantic oceanic signals to European precipitation patterns.

Figure 7: Left: Difference in anomaly correlation coefficient (ACC) for wintertime (DJFM) precipitation at forecast years 1–10 between initialized decadal predictions and corresponding uninitialized historical simulations. Right: ACC for winter precipitation obtained from the hybrid model based on SPNA-SST and NAO indices for forecast years 1–10. Statistical significance is assessed using a one-sided Student's t-test, accounting for autocorrelation by considering the effective sample size (Bretherton et al., 1999). Adapted from Nicoli et al. (2025).

Ocean–atmosphere feedbacks key to NAO decadal predictability (CMCC)

This part of the CMCC contribution is based on Patrizio et al. (2025). Recent studies using initialised large-ensemble re-forecasts have shown that the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) exhibits significant decadal predictability, which is of great importance to society given the significant climate anomalies that accompany the NAO. However, the key physical processes underlying this predictability, including the role of ocean–atmosphere interactions, have not yet been pinned down. Also, a critical deficiency in the representation of the associated predictable signal by climate models has been identified in recent studies (the signal-to-noise problem), still lacking an explanation. In this study, the decadal prediction skill for the NAO and the interactions of the associated atmospheric circulation anomalies with the underlying ocean are assessed using retrospective forecasts from eight decadal prediction systems (DPSs) and observation-based data. We find considerable spread in the NAO skill across these systems and critically, that this is linked to differences in the representation of ocean–NAO interactions across the systems (Figure 8). It was found that the NAO skill depends on a direct positive feedback between subpolar sea surface temperature anomalies and the NAO (not shown), which varies in strength

across the prediction systems, yet may still be too weak even in the most skillful systems compared to the observational estimate. This positive feedback is opposed by a delayed negative feedback between the NAO and the ocean circulation that also contributes to disparities in the NAO skill across systems (not shown). Our findings therefore suggest that North Atlantic ocean–atmosphere interactions are central to NAO decadal predictability. Finally, it is suggested that errors in the representation of these interactions may be contributing significantly to the signal-to-noise problem.

Figure 8: (a) Anomaly correlation coefficient (ACC) for the NAO calculated using linearly detrended winter-mean sea-level pressure fields from ERA5 and 10-member ensembles for all DPSs (black circles), and for full ensembles (asterisks) from the CMCC (20 members), CESM (40 members) and CanESM5 (20 members) DPSs. Solid markers indicate ACCs that are outside the 5–95th percentiles of the ACC distribution of 2000 block-bootstrap samples (gray bars) and are considered statistically significant. The 10-member ACCs for CMCC, CESM and CanESM5 DPSs are calculated by averaging the ACCs over 500 random combinations of 10-member subensembles (circles) and the associated 5–95th percentiles are shown for CMCC and CESM (black whiskers). Red circles indicate ACCs calculated from the respective 10-member uninitialized historical simulations. Light blue markers indicate the ACC for detrended annual-mean SSTs averaged over the subpolar region indicated by the green frame in b. (b) ACC for North Atlantic SSTs calculated using linearly detrended annual-mean SST fields from ERA5 and full-ensembles for each DPS. Areas without stippling indicate ACCs that are statistically significant. The green frames indicate the subpolar averaging region used in later figures (50°N–65°N, 10°W–55°W). In both panels, the DPS fields have been averaged over forecast years 1–8, while an 8-year running average has been applied to ERA5 fields before calculating the ACC.

The NAO decadal predictability determined by the initial ocean heat content in the subpolar North Atlantic (CMCC)

In recent studies using large ensembles, the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) has been shown to exhibit significant decadal predictability stemming from skillfully predicted sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies in the subpolar North Atlantic (SPNA). In turn, various studies have demonstrated that the decadal SST predictability in this area is dominantly due to ocean initialization. It remains unclear, however, which component of the oceanic initial conditions determines the evolution of the SPNA SSTs and the NAO in the following years, and which dynamical processes are involved. The results presented below were obtained in an ongoing study (manuscript in preparation) in which we assess

the role of initial upper-ocean heat content (OHC) anomalies in the SPNA in four decadal prediction systems exhibiting significant skill for the wintertime NAO. First, using observations, it is found that the NAO averaged in several successive winters is significantly correlated with the SPNA OHC in the November preceding the first winter (Figure 9). Second, it is shown that this relationship holds also in the decadal prediction systems, and it is stronger in the systems that exhibit higher skill for the NAO itself (not shown). Finally, we discuss the causal chain that leads from skillfully predicted SSTs to the NAO predictability via changes in low-level baroclinicity and positive feedbacks internal to the atmosphere. Even though multi-decadal variations in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) may play a key role in determining respective historical variations in the SPNA OHC, no AMOC anomalies were found in the initial conditions of the hindcasts that could explain the subsequent evolution of the NAO. Of course, this result does not preclude an important role for the AMOC in real-world NAO predictability. Our findings advance the understanding of the mechanisms underlying decadal predictability and raise new questions regarding the role of model fidelity and ocean–NAO feedbacks in relation to the signal-to-noise problem.

Figure 9: Upper-ocean heat content (OHC) anomalies in November regressed onto the forward 8-year mean NAO for (a) EN4 and ERA5, (b) *top members* and (c) *bottom members* from the CMCC Decadal Prediction System. “Top members” and “bottom members”, as in Patrizio et al. (2025), refer to combinations of individual forecasts exhibiting, correspondingly, best and worst agreement with the observed NAO variations.

External forcing of the NAO (Met Office)

The Met Office has investigated external forcing of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) on multi-decadal timescales (Smith et al 2025). A key discovery is that different models can have very different, even opposite, NAO responses to the same forcings (Fig 10a). Where models have different responses we should no longer use the multi-model ensemble mean because the true response could be like any of the models, and if there are signal to noise errors it might not be captured by any of the models.

Smith et al (2025) exploited the model differences by developing an emergent constraint to narrow the uncertainties in the projections. They found that some of the model spread could be explained by background water vapour differences in the models. Background water vapour influences the latitude of changes in the meridional temperature gradient at the tropopause (the hygropause latitude) which shifts the winds and affects the NAO. Specifically, the hygropause latitude relative to the climatological jet latitude controls the shift of the winds, and is correlated across the models with external forcings measured by Earth’s energy imbalance (Fig 10b).

Taking models at face value by using the multi-model ensemble mean shows no correlation with the observations over the historical period (Fig 10c). This would imply the NAO is not externally forced, and that the difference between the observations and multi-model mean is due to unpredictable internal variability, albeit extremely rare at the observed maximum which is barely captured by the model spread. However, exploiting model differences in an emergent constraint reveals a significant correlation with observations, suggesting an externally forced NAO response. Importantly, it also reveals that the magnitude of variability of the constrained simulations is too small relative to the high correlation, consistent with the signal to noise paradox (Scaife and Smith 2018), and must be scaled (by a factor of 4 in this case) to achieve realistic and reliable simulations. Calibrating the projections to account for model differences and signal to noise errors suggests the multi-decadal NAO will increase to unprecedented levels around three times larger than seen since 1850 under the high emission scenario (SSP585), but this can be avoided by mitigation to reduce levels of greenhouse gasses (Fig 10d).

Figure 10: Exploiting model differences to improve projections to understand drivers a, Time series of observed NAO (black curve, Hadley Centre Sea Level Pressure (HadSLP)) and ensemble mean historical and SSP2-4.5 simulations for selected models. The correlation with observations and the Ratio of Predictable

Signals (RPS, if significant at the 5% level) are indicated. b, Scatter plot of detrended historical northern hemisphere 200-hPa jet latitude shift related to EEI against climatological 200-hPa hygropause latitude relative to the jet (Methods). The correlation is indicated along with the line of best fit (black) and the observed 200-hPa tropopause latitude relative to the jet (vertical grey line). c, Time series of observed NAO (black curves: thick, HadSLP dataset; thin, Twentieth Century Reanalysis (20CR) dataset) and historical and projected (with scenarios SSP5-8.5, SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6) multi-model simulations (colours, multi-model ensemble mean solid curve, 5–95% confidence interval diagnosed from ensemble members shaded). The correlation between simulated and observed NAO is indicated. d, As for c but for calibrated simulations based on the emergent constraint shown in b and the RPS, with shading showing the 5–95% confidence interval diagnosed from the r.m.s.e.. All data are for boreal winter (October–March) 31-year rolling means.

The mechanism driving changes in the NAO is largely revealed by Hovmuller plots (Fig 11). Changes in the meridional temperature gradient at the tropopause (200 hPa) will shift the zonal mean winds, as shown by many studies with simple models. Volcanic eruptions cool the equatorial region (shown by the hist-nat panel), creating a positive meridional temperature gradient that shifts the winds equatorward, driving a tendency towards a negative NAO. Conversely, greenhouse gases warm the equatorial region, creating a negative meridional temperature gradient that shifts the winds poleward, driving a tendency towards a positive NAO. Importantly, once the winds have shifted, further changes in the meridional temperature gradient (i.e. trends) are needed to change the NAO (Fig 11b,c). Under the high emission scenario (SSP585) the meridional temperature gradient keeps reducing, leading to NAO projections to unprecedented levels, that would lead to more flooding and storminess. When mitigation occurs in the mid-century for SSP245 and earlier in SSP126, the meridional temperature gradient increases and the NAO reduces.

Fig. 11: Physical mechanism driving the NAO. a, Latitude–year Hovmuller plots of zonal mean temperature at 200 hPa relative to the preceding 30-year mean, shown for rolling 31-year means. Panels are shown for the historical, hist-nat, SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 unweighted multi-model ensemble means. Vertical

lines indicate 35° N. b, Time series of calibrated hist-nat NAO (thin yellow line, left axis) and multi-model ensemble mean 31-year rolling trend of $-dT/d(lat)$ at 35° N (thick yellow line, right axis, minus sign because $dT/d(lat)$ is negative in the Northern Hemisphere). c, As for b but for historical simulations and future projections. All data are for boreal winter (October–March).

There was a meeting of the WCRP Lighthouse activity on Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change in July 2025. A key outcome was to agree an analysis plan for large ensemble model simulations (Fig 12). It follows from the ASPECT study of Smith et al (2025) and accounts for model differences and errors. The recommendation is very different from the current standard practice. In particular, it emphasises to stop using the multi-model ensemble mean if models show different responses, because the true response could be like any of the models, and if there are signal to noise errors it might not be captured by any of the models. It also emphasises the need to assess potential signal to noise errors, since if they exist, the impacts of climate change, and future changes in climate, could be more severe than expected as shown in Smith et al (2025). Another important recommendation is to not use the spread of the members if there are signal to noise errors because the modelled internal variability will be incorrect.

Large Ensemble Analysis Plan

- **1. Stop using multi-model ensemble mean if models show different responses** – we can't rule out that the true response isn't like any of the models, and if there are signal to noise errors it might not be like any of the models
- **2. Try to work out the true response** – by exploiting model differences
- **3. Test for signal to noise errors** – by computing ratio of predictable components
- **4. Stop assuming the ensemble member spread is a true measure internal variability**, because if there are signal-to-noise errors, modelled internal variability will be incorrect and needs to be adjusted

Figure 12: Analysis plan agreed at the meeting of the WCRP Lighthouse activity on Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change in July 2025.

Decadal and long-term trends in the North Atlantic in single forcing experiments (MPG)

The Large Ensemble Single Forcing Model Intercomparison Project (LESFMIP) Multi-annual to decadal changes in climate are accompanied by changes in extreme events that cause major impacts on society and severe challenges for adaptation. Early warnings of such changes are now potentially possible through operational decadal predictions. However, improved understanding of the causes of regional changes in climate on these time scales is needed both to attribute recent events to the climate change forcings and to gain further confidence in the forecasts. The Large Ensemble Single Forcing Model Intercomparison Project (LESFMIP) addresses this need through coordinated model experiments enabling the impacts of different external drivers to be isolated (Smith et al., 2022). Here, several partners contributed to the analysis of the

LESMIP, and accomplished and provided large ensemble runs via Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF).

MPI has performed historical-like simulations with the climate model MPI-ESM-LR for LESFMIP (Smith et al., 2022). The following historical-like 30 members ensemble simulations are completed: greenhouse gasses-only (hist-GHG), total-ozone-only (hist-totalO3), anthropogenic aerosols-only (hist-aer), volcanic aerosols-only (hist-volc), solar-only (hist-sol) and natural-only (hist-nat). As a first step, the single forcing simulations are compared with historical simulations over the period 1850–2014. The global mean surface air temperature shows a warming trend for the historical, hist-GHG, and hist-totalO3 simulations and a cooling trend for the hist-aer and hist-volc simulations. The surface air temperature difference between the last 20 years (i.e., 1995–2014) and the first 20 years (i.e., 1850–1869) of the simulation period is in most regions positive in the historical, hist-GHG and the hist-totalO3 experiments except in the region of the subpolar gyre in the North Atlantic referred to the “warming hole”. A different - largely opposite - pattern emerges in the hist-aer simulations. Changing ocean currents are found to be key for the mechanism leading to the North Atlantic warming hole (Pohlmann et al. submitted).

Extreme Event Attribution Framework in Seasonal Forecast (UOXF)

UOXF studied the recent unprecedented 2022 Pakistan flood event. A modelling approach is proposed for event attribution in context of climate changes. The following experiments are conducted:

Fig. 13 illustrates the modelling approach in the study: The experiments preIND and FUTURE are performed specifically for this study. Changes were applied to the CO₂ concentration during the forecasts and perturbations to the ocean and sea-ice state at the start of the forecasts. The perturbations to the initial conditions reflect the adjustment of the global oceans to the decreased and increased CO₂ concentrations.

Further, Experiments A and B use perturbed CO₂ concentrations but the same initial conditions as SEAS5. Experiment A estimates past direct SST contribution, while experiment B reveals the future direct CO₂ contribution and neglects changes in the ocean. All 4 experiments are performed with a similar ensemble size as the operation forecasts of SEAS5. For details, please see Weisheimer et al (2025).

Figure 13: Schematic illustrating the design of the forecast attribution experiments and the direct atmospheric contributions from CO₂ and SST perturbations to the total climate changes signals; Weisheimer et al. (2025).

Figure 14: **a** Histograms with the light grey showing JJA precipitation in ERA5 over the 24-year climatological reference period 1993–2016. The dark grey histograms show JJA precipitation in SEAS5 over the same period estimated from all 51 hindcast ensemble members. Forecast distributions for JJA 2022 from the 51 SEAS5 (red), preIND (dark blue) and FUTURE (yellow) ensemble members. The dotted vertical lines in all panels indicate the amount of rainfall during JJA 2022 in ERA5 and GPCP. The dashed vertical line in all panels indicates the rainfall threshold of the upper quintile of the SEAS5 climatological distribution. The inset numbers indicate the ensemble mean and standard deviation for each forecast ensemble. All histograms have been normalised such that the sum of the bar areas equals 1. **b** Cumulative distributions of precipitation in ERA5, GPCP and for the different simulations; Weisheimer et al. (2025).

Figure 14a shows histograms and cumulative distribution (Fig. 14b) of JJA absolute rainfall averaged over Pakistan for the SEAS5 seasonal forecasts and the two counterfactual forecasts preIND and FUTURE. The climatological distributions of ERA5, GPCP and SEAS5 during the 1993–2016 period are shown in different shades of grey colour. The climatological distribution of SEAS5 is based on 51 ensemble members in the hindcasts, resulting in a much finer histogram and smoother distributions than the observed datasets. There is a remarkably good agreement between the model climatology and the ERA5/GPCP distributions, with comparable levels of variability and only a very small dry bias in the hindcasts.

With the 51-member operational SEAS5 forecast plotted in red, both the histograms and cumulative distributions highlight the shift to extremely wet conditions in JJA 2022 compared to the SEAS5 hindcast climatology. This shift towards higher rainfall impacts not only the mean but the entire forecast distribution including the dry and wet extremes. Fig. 14b represents the climatological SEAS5 upper quintile threshold of 2.37 mm/day (i.e., 80th climatological percentile of the seasonal mean rainfall distribution, see dashed vertical line) that exceeded by approximately 70% of the SEAS5 forecast ensemble members. The wettest forecast member produces slightly more rain than ERA5 and GPCP.

The distributions of both counterfactual ensembles, shown in Fig. 14 in dark blue for the preIND reduced CO₂ concentration experiment and in yellow for the FUTURE increased CO₂ concentration experiment, are also clearly shifted towards wetter-than-normal conditions, similarly to SEAS5. By taking the quantile of the cumulative forecast distributions in Fig. 14b at the climatological upper quintile precipitation threshold, we estimate that the probability of exceeding the climatological SEAS5 upper quintile in preIND is nearly 50% which implies that the risk of high precipitation amounts is still greatly increased over its reference climatological value of 20%, yet not as much as in the SEAS5 forecast using current-day CO₂ concentrations. Equally, the FUTURE probability of exceeding the upper quintile (i.e., 55%) remains strongly enhanced over its climatological reference, though less so than in SEAS5.

Figure 15: Anomaly of the zonal wind at 200 hPa (U200) during JJA 2022 in (a) ERA5, (b) SEAS5 ensemble mean and (c) the ensemble member with the strongest precipitation anomaly over Pakistan. The blue thick lines indicate the reversal of tropical easterlies to extratropical westerly flow. The cyan coloured boxes in (a–c) show the area over the Tibetan Plateau that is used to define the zonal flow index. d Scatter diagram of the relationship between the zonal flow index and precipitation anomaly over Pakistan in the SEAS5 forecast ensemble. The ensemble member with the highest precipitation anomaly is highlighted. U200 climate change signals of JJA 2022 in the past (e) and for the future (f). Climate change signals are defined as the difference between simulations with stronger CO₂ and SST forcings minus simulations with weaker CO₂ and SST forcings. The past climate change signal (e) is estimated as SEAS5 minus preIND; the future climate change signal (f) is estimated from FUTURE minus SEAS5. Wind units: m/s; **Weisheimer et al. (2025)**.

An important aspect to the extreme wet season in Pakistan is the anomalous zonal flow over the Tibetan Plateau. In summer, the climatological high potential temperatures over the western Tibetan Plateau together with the climatological upper-tropospheric subtropical westerly flow generate descending vertical motion to the west and ascent further east. Climatological descent to the west is associated with warming and drying and has a direct effect on maximum temperatures and precipitation at the surface. On the downstream eastern side of the plateau, the ascending vertical motion leads to a wetter climate over sub-tropical East Asia.

In JJA 2022, however, the westerly wind circulation in the upper troposphere over Tibet and surrounding areas was substantially weaker than in its long-term climatological mean. The resulting negative zonal wind anomalies at 200 hPa in ERA5 are shown in Fig. 15a. With the blue line indicating the region of easterly upper tropospheric winds in the tropics, these anomalies can be interpreted as an expansion of the tropical easterly regime and a northward shift of the westerly jet. The SEAS5 forecasts correctly predicted large-scale easterly anomalies over subtropical Asia and the Tibetan Plateau (Fig. 15b), yet differences of zonal flow anomalies exist across the ensemble, manifesting in a weaker

ensemble mean circulation anomaly locally over Pakistan and an eastward shift of the maxima of the circulation anomalies.

Based on reanalysis and observational data, it has been demonstrated elsewhere that the easterly flow anomalies in the upper troposphere over the Tibetan Plateau during the summer 2022 dynamically induced strong ascent to the west of the plateau, leading to the observed positive rainfall anomalies in Pakistan. To test whether a similar dynamic mechanism is active in our forecasts, we quantify the relationship between the large-scale upper tropospheric circulation and rainfall over Pakistan by defining a zonal flow index as the mean zonal wind anomaly at 200 hPa over a region above the Tibetan Plateau where the strongest easterly wind anomalies occurred (cyan box in Fig. 15a, see methods; Weisheimer et al. 2025). The zonal flow index of the ERA5 anomaly is -5.1 m/s, for the ensemble mean of SEAS5 it is -2.6 m/s with the largest negative anomaly within the ensemble being -5.3 m/s.

The scatterplot of the SEAS5 zonal flow index anomalies for each ensemble member against its rainfall anomaly in Pakistan in Fig. 15d clearly shows that our model captures the described observed relationship between the large-scale circulation anomaly and rainfall over Pakistan, with the correlation of $r = -0.39$ being highly significant ($p = 0.004$). Indeed, the ensemble member with the highest rainfall also shows the strongest upper air easterly wind anomaly (Fig. 15c).

Fig. 15e, f, indicates, in the past the total climate change signal showed a mean weakening of the westerly zonal flow component by approximately 0.3 m/s (Fig. 15e), consistent with a weak increase in precipitation. In contrast, the future climate change signal shows a mean strengthening of the westerly flow component by approximately 0.9 m/s (Fig. 15f), consistent with the weak decrease in precipitation found in the simulations. The statistical relationship between the ensemble rainfall anomalies over Pakistan and the upper tropospheric zonal flow index is slightly reduced in the preIND counterfactual simulation ($r = -0.34$ with $p = 0.015$) and slightly strengthened in the FUTURE simulation ($r = -0.46$ with $p = 0.001$). As with the precipitation sensitivities, the circulation signals induced by changes in the CO_2 and SST forcings are small compared to the magnitude of the upper tropospheric wind anomaly (approximately 10% and 30%).

Using experiments **A** and **B**, the total CO_2 -induced climate change signal of rainfall in Pakistan is decomposed into its effects due to the direct atmospheric response to CO_2 and due to the SST climate change response. In the past, the direct CO_2 effect primarily contributed to the increase in precipitation. For future CO_2 climate changes, the dryer signal over Pakistan is dominated by the SST effect, whereas the direct atmospheric response to CO_2 changes alone would indicate a weak wet signal. Importantly though, it is the magnitude of their relative change that controls the total dynamical response, leading to the non-linear rainfall response signal over Pakistan. For further details, please see Weisheimer et al. (2025).

3 Summary

The presented work feeds to the physical understanding underpinning climate prediction at different timescales. Every investigation makes a fundamental contribution to understanding the origin of predictive accuracy. On **seasonal timescales**, the investigation on trends in the tropical Pacific reveal model errors in a seasonal prediction system and highlight that a simple trend-aware calibration of the forecasts can improve forecast accuracy (**ECMWF**). Further, the dynamic property of Rossby wave sources is considered and highlights how remote sources in the Pacific alter the European summer climate (**SMHI**). Fundamental properties of the coupled North Atlantic climate system are established on **sub-decadal and decadal timescale**. A new story-line is established linking coupled damped oscillation of the North Atlantic climate system for European summer extremes, their predictions as utilization such as growing degree days (**MPG**). Several studies have deepened our understanding of the decadal predictability of the NAO, and forms the basis for a further storyline (CMCC). These investigations underline the role of ocean initialization and ocean–atmosphere feedbacks for NAO predictions. **Long-term forced changes** are investigated for the Atlantic European sector. An examination with respect to the NAO shows that model spread is caused by differences in background water vapor, allowing an emergent constraint to be developed to better estimate a true response (**Met Office**). Exploiting model differences in an emergent constraint reveals a significant correlation with observations, suggesting an externally forced NAO response. Externally forced responses are also examined for the North Atlantic sub-polar gyre. Results show warming from greenhouse gases and ozone, cooling from aerosols and volcanoes, and highlight the North Atlantic “warming hole” caused by ocean circulation changes (**MPG**). Further, an event attribution approach that can be used to attribute climate extreme events in climate change context and possible drivers (**UOX**). As a case study the Pakistan flood 2022 is examined.

In the following, summaries of the partners are given in more detail.

Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M)

MPI-M contributes to D2.2 through the **LESFMIP project**, which investigates how different climate forcings affect regional climate variability. Using the **MPI-ESM-LR model**, MPI-M ran ensemble simulations isolating the effects of greenhouse gases, aerosols, volcanic, and solar forcings. Results show warming from greenhouse gases and ozone, cooling from aerosols and volcanoes, and highlight the North Atlantic “warming hole” caused by ocean circulation changes (Pohlmann et al., submitted).

Additionally, MPI-M identified a sub-decadal mechanism linking **North Atlantic heat accumulation** to **extremely warm European summers**, improving the potential for early prediction of such events (Wallberg et al., 2024, 2025).

ECMWF

ECMWF has investigated the errors in trends in the operational SEAS5 seasonal forecasts. Trends of observed tropical Pacific sea surface temperatures (SSTs) in recent decades have been toward a more La Niña–like state. Numerous studies over the past decade have shown that ensemble mean trends from historical climate model simulations

from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and large-ensemble simulations exhibit an error in the trends, showing the so-called “Pacific Warming Pattern”. Here we show that the ECMWF operational seasonal forecasting system SEAS5 hindcasts also exhibit a trend error similar to the Pacific Warming Pattern, with underestimation the observed strengthening of equatorial easterly and cross-equatorial southerly winds, and associated SST warming in the Eastern Pacific. This tendency persisted during the 2020–22 triple-dip La Niña, with forecast errors reminiscent of the long-term trend errors. performance in recent years, but ultimately these errors should be corrected by improving models, since accurate representation of the tropical Pacific climate is critically important for both initialized predictions and projections.

Met Office

The Met Office has studied external forcing of the **North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)** on multi-decadal timescales (Smith et al. 2025). It was found that different models can have very different, even **opposite**, responses to the same forcings. In this case, the multi-model ensemble mean should not be used since the true response could be like any of the models, and if there are **signal to noise errors** it might not be captured by any of the models. Instead, it is crucial to try to find the true response and to test for signal to noise errors.

It was found that some of the model spread was caused by differences in background **water vapour**, allowing an emergent constraint to be developed to better estimate the true response. This constrained timeseries is significantly correlated with observation, revealing a forced response that is not seen in the multi-model ensemble mean. Importantly, a signal to noise error is also revealed such that the response must be scaled by ~four times to achieve realistic and reliable projections. This suggests that under a high emission scenario multi-decadal NAO will increase to **unprecedented** levels around three times larger than seen in the instrumental record. However, this can be avoided through **mitigation** to reduce levels of greenhouse gases.

SMHI

SMHI has studied how Rossby Wave Sources (RWS) originating over the northeastern Pacific modulate summer atmospheric circulation across the Northern Hemisphere and influence precipitation over Northern Europe. Using ERA5 reanalysis and large ensembles from several CMIP6 global models, the work shows that intensified Pacific RWS generate a circumglobal wavetrain that propagates along the Pacific–North America–Atlantic–European sector, altering geopotential height, temperature, and precipitation.

When comparing how the large ensembles represent RWS with ERA5, we find that in ERA5 summer RWS climatology forms coherent dipole structures aligned with the upper-level subtropical jets and monsoon outflows, with strong sources over the northeastern Pacific and sinks over the western basins. Most of the large-ensembles capture the main spatial patterns of RWS and the resulting wavetrain linking the Pacific and European sectors, although with varying phase and intensity. The circumglobal response features alternating high- and low-pressure anomalies, with a robust negative

geopotential-height node over the North Atlantic–Nordic region, consistent with enhanced storminess and precipitation over Northern Europe. Inter-model differences are largest over the Atlantic–European node, where phase shifts or amplitude biases affect the strength of the teleconnection. These systematic errors found in the different large ensembles point to persistent challenges in simulating upper-tropospheric divergence and jet dynamics, highlighting the Atlantic sector as the critical bottleneck controlling how Pacific forcing influences European summer climate.

UOXF

UOXF has proposed an event attribution approach that can be used to attribute climate extreme events in climate change context and possible drivers. The Pakistan 2022 event was studied with this approach. A number of important implications can be drawn from this study. Relevant to the loss and damage issue, the results suggest that past anthropogenically caused climate change due to CO₂ does exacerbate the rainfall amounts over Pakistan in summer 2022 by approximately 0.3 mm/day. In absolute terms, however, this increase is small: around 10% of the SEAS5-simulated absolute rainfall amount of 2.71 mm/day for JJA 2022. Contrary to a linear projection of this signal into the future, the experiments show that a future anthropogenic increase in CO₂ concentrations would not necessarily lead to a further exacerbation of Pakistan rainfall; instead, a non-significant reduction by approximately 5% of the ensemble mean rainfall has been found. However, we also see a tendency that wet extremes might become more likely in the future climate, and hence Pakistan should indeed be prepared.

This study is also relevant to the issue of climate adaptation and, on a broader scale, to the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. Moreover, the attribution approach discussed in the study can be adopted for climate extreme events across the globe, eventually helping the identification of their drivers.

CMCC

CMCC presented results from three published studies conducted in ASPECT WP2, specifically: [Patrizio et al. \(2025\)](#); [Nicoli et al. \(2025\)](#) and [Tsartsali et al. \(2025\)](#) and two ongoing analyses (mutli-authored manuscripts in preparation), all dealing with climate predictability in multi-annual to decadal predictions. Our work underlines the role of ocean initialization and ocean–atmosphere feedbacks, particularly those related to the NAO, in determining both the associated predictability found in state-of-the-art decadal predictions, as well as the system’s limitations in realistically representing some key physical processes underpinning this predictability. Then, the above-presented analysis on the predictability of temperature extremes in multi-annual predictions, which is the first published on this topic, showed promising results regarding the usability of such novel predictions.

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